

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

No. 58 - November 2017 · www.ioc-unesco.org/hab

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

Call to Contribute to Global Harmful Algal Bloom Status Reporting

From 25 to 28 September 2017 sixteen HAB experts from 13 countries gathered at the headquarters of the IOC IODE (International Oceanographic Data Exchange) Programme Office in Oostende, Belgium (see group picture in the back page), to receive training in data entry into the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS; <http://www.iobis.org>) and the Harmful Algae Event Database (HAEDAT; <http://haedat.iode.org>). Editors within defined HAB regions were requested to collect publications associated with the **occurrences of toxic algae**, even with no recorded impact, and enter these records in OBIS. The aim is to trace reliable geographic ranges for the genera/species that are included in the IOC Taxonomic Reference List of toxic and ichthyotoxic algae (<http://www.marinespecies.org/hab>). This activity will complement the compilation of **records of harmful events with impacts** (including cases of intoxicated seafood, discolorations, mucilages, etc.) collected in HAEDAT, with new event data being entered from regions for which this information is currently missing. The effort of compiling and increasing data sets is being intensified

in order to provide a substantial part of the basis for a first Global HAB Status Report.

This report series will provide the scientific community as well as decision makers with a reference on HAB occurrence and impacts on ecosystem services. IOC-UNESCO project partners include the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES), the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES) and the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (IS-SHA). We hope that the establishment of these data bases will allow us to convincingly answer key questions on the probability of change in HAB frequencies, intensities, and geographic range resulting from environmental changes at local and global scales. While the available data sets are still incomplete, we here provide examples of analyses from HAEDAT (Figs. 1, 2, 4) and OBIS (Fig. 3) data. While the results are preliminary and conclusions are likely to be modified as more data become available, we present them as an encouragement for HAB workers to contribute to this important initiative.

Fig. 1. Total number of HAEDAT records in the different OBIS regions of East Coast America, West Coast America, Caribbean Central America, Northern Europe, Southern Europe, Mediterranean, Australia/New Zealand, North Asia and Pacific. The regions of South America, Africa and South East Asia represent key missing data sets. Data as of 1/3/2017. Compiled by Laura Schweibold who worked for 6 months on a GHSR Masters project supervised by G.Hallegraeff.

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COMING SOON

ICHA
BRAZIL 2016

MARINE AND FRESH-WATER
HARMFUL ALGAE

PROCEEDINGS OF THE 17th
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAE

9-14 October 2016 | Florianópolis, Brazil

Fig. 2. Partitioning of 5136 global HAEDAT events into seafood toxins, high biomass water discolorations, fauna mass mortalities, and the further breakdown of seafood toxins into DSP, PSP, ASP, NSP, CFP, AZP and cyanotoxins. Data as of 1/3/2017. Compiled by Laura Schweibold.

Different regions and countries suffer from different types of HABs, and this is reflected in the way countries/regions enter their data. North America and Europe operate highly sophisticated shellfish toxin monitoring programs. PSP is the dominant seafood toxin syndrome in North America, NSP in the Gulf of Mexico and DSP in Europe. The effectiveness of these monitoring programmes is well reflected in the fact that only an estimated 1 to 10% of toxin-producing blooms lead to human poisonings. In contrast in less well monitored areas such as Australia/New Zealand and Central America up to 50 to 60% of toxin producing algal bloom events can lead to human victims. In the extreme, Pacific HAEDAT data are based exclusively on human ciguatera poisonings diagnosed by medical practitioners.

OBIS HAB species occurrence data are even more incomplete, and heavily biased by European records. Time series data for location records of the key target genera *Dinophysis* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* (Fig. 3) exhibit an increase in frequency over the past 30 years, undoubtedly reflective of increased awareness and monitoring effort.

The ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD) have used HAEDAT to map the distribution of harmful algal events during the period from 2014 to 2016 in the North Atlantic. Examples for PSP, DSP and AZP are presented in Fig. 4. These maps highlight the regional aspect to harmful algal events in the North

Atlantic area with PSP events recorded across the USA, Canada and Europe during the three year period, a higher incidence of DSP events recorded in Europe, and AZP events restricted to the SW coast of Ireland with a low number also recorded in the UK and Norway.

Planned outputs of the Global HAB Status Report include: (1) a dedicated session during ICHA18 in Nantes in October 2018; (2) a special issue of Harmful Algae in 2019; (3) regular 2-3 year reports on the status of global HABs,

the first of which will be launched in Nantes.

Follow the development of the Global HAB Status Report at <http://haedat.iode.org/> and see who is involved and how you may engage.

Acknowledgements

We thank Ward Appeltans and Pieter Provoost at the IOC/IODE Project Office for hospitality and technical support. The meeting was funded by the Flanders Government through the Ocean Teacher Global Academy and DIPS-4-ocean assessments projects.

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Fig. 3. Time series of OBIS location records of the HAB genera *Dinophysis* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* between 1950 and 2014, with the time of description of their associated syndromes DSP and ASP indicated. Records are heavily biased towards Europe.

Fig. 4. Maps showing the incidence of PSP, DSP and AZP during the period 2014 to 2016 in the North Atlantic as reported by the ICES-IOC WG HABD. Areas such as Northern Canada and Greenland are not routinely sampled and countries with pink borders have still to submit data. Data from the Pacific shorelines of Canada and the USA are also included.

Pelagic *Sargassum* reaching Serranilla Bank, Caribbean Colombia, may pose a risk to baby turtles

Fig. 1. Location of Serranilla Bank in the Caribbean Sea (Photo Wikipedia)

Floating *Sargassum* has been known from centuries to occur in the Atlantic Ocean, in a region named the Sargasso Sea. Floating *Sargassum* mats can form a pelagic ecosystem comprised by two species, *S. fluitans* and *S. natans*, which support a high variety of species associated with them [1]. It has been estimated that the Sargasso Sea harbors about 10 million tons of wet biomass [2]. Although deposits of *Sargassum* occur naturally and regularly on beaches, since 2011 enormous quantities of these seaweeds have been washed ashore in the Caribbean Sea, Gulf of Mexico, and, in 2011, even reached the West coast of Africa [3-5]. Multiple hypotheses have been proposed to explain such events, amongst which stand the excess of nutrient loads, a change in trade currents, and global climate change [6].

To some extent, *Sargassum* biomass may be beneficial to the environment, because it provides food and shelter to a number of organisms, it may help fight beach erosion and provides nutrients to beach habitats [6]. However, when biomass is very high, it may have negative effects: the accumulation of algae on the sea surface precludes light penetration and affect corals, sea grasses and benthic macroalgae [7]. Drift algae on the beach may become a barrier to nesting turtles and/or to baby turtles finding their way to the ocean [7-9]. Cleaning up the excessive biomass along the beaches may enhance beach erosion [6] and decomposition on the shore may change water chemistry and induce hypoxia, with consequent fish die-off [10].

Serranilla Bank is an ancient atoll in the Caribbean Sea, at 15° 50' N and 79°

50' W (Fig. 1). It has several small keys emerging from the water to form some permanent islands. These small islands, far from other emerged territories, have been recognized recently as important nesting areas for sea turtles (Barrientos-Muñoz and Ramirez-Gallego, pers. comm.).

In September 2017, the Colombian Commission for the Ocean (CCO), with the participation of other Colombian agencies and institutions (Colciencias, Dimar) and the logistic support of the Colombian Navy (Armada de Colombia), organized a scientific expedition to Serranilla Bank. During this expedition, which is the first and largest effort to date to study the biodiversity of this remote area of Colombia, we observed a large amount of floating *Sargassum* reaching the beaches of Beacon Key, the largest island in Serranilla Bank (Fig. 2). The algae accumulated on the beaches, and formed a thick 40 cm high mat (Fig. 3). On the beach, there were a large number of turtle nests (Barrientos-Muñoz and Ramirez-Gallego, pers. comm.) which, by the time of the *Sargassum* wave, were ready to disclose and the baby turtles go to sea. Some baby turtles were observed having troubles passing the barrier posed by the *Sargassum* mat (Fig. 4), and were vulnerable to predation by ghost crabs, rats and other predators.

Considering that all the sea turtles species in the Caribbean are at risk of extinction, large amounts of *Sargassum* in Serranilla Bank may pose an additional threat to the survival of these organisms.

Acknowledgements

The authors are greatly indebted to the Comisión Colombiana del Océano (CCO), to the Armada Nacional de Colombia, to Colciencias, and to Dimar for organizing the Scientific Expedition *Seaflower* 2017, Serranilla Bank. We thank Karla Georgina Barrientos-Muñoz and Cristian Ramirez-Gallego, from the Fundación Tortugas del Mar, for sharing their knowledge on sea turtles and Santiago Estrada-Robledo, from the Reef Shepherd Scuba diving school, for the aerial photo of *Sargassum*. The present study was financed by Universidad Nacional de Colombia, sede Caribe.

Fig. 2. Aerial photo of drifting *Sargassum* reaching Beacon Key. (Photo credits: Santiago Estrada-Robledo)

Fig. 3. *Sargassum* accumulation as a thick mat on the nesting beach

Fig. 4. A baby turtle struggling to find its way through the *Sargassum* mat

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NEW!! Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and Desalination: A Guide to Impacts, Monitoring, and Management

UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission has launched the first ever guidebook on the growing problem HABs pose to seawater desalination plants. The launch took place last October at the International Desalination Association World Congress in São Paulo Brazil.

This guidebook is published to help the desalination industry tackle an issue that represents a potential threat both to human health and to the distribution of desalinated water on which an increasing number of arid countries rely for their fresh water needs.

The 517-page manual is a groundbreaking achievement built on the cooperation of 63 HAB and desalination industry specialists from multiple disciplines, some of which had rarely interacted in the past.

The publication was sponsored by the Middle East Desalination Research Center (MEDRC), the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the IOC of UNESCO. It was edited by Don Anderson, Siobhan Boerlage and Mike Dixon.

Copies of the manual can be ordered online at <http://www.ioc-unesco.org/HAB-desalination>

A red tide event associated with the dinoflagellate *Karenia mikimotoi* in the Firth of Clyde, Scotland

Fig. 1. Maximum abundance of *K. mikimotoi* by month and year for monitoring sites in Scottish coastal waters. The densest bloom observed exceeded 4 million cells per litre in July 2016.

The potentially harmful dinoflagellate species *Karenia mikimotoi* has been an occasional red tide forming species in Scottish waters since the 1980s. In 2006 a bloom detected off the west coast of Scotland covered an exceptionally large area, progressing around the Scottish coast and leading to mass mortalities of benthic invertebrates and wild fish [1]. Since then regular monitoring has been undertaken by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS), revealing recurrent blooms in late summer (Fig. 1). In addition to this, occurrences have been recorded at monitoring stations administered by Marine Science Scotland (MSS) and the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA).

In July 2016 SAMS alerted SEPA and MSS to increasing observations of *K. mikimotoi* in seawater samples collected from coastal sites around southwest Scotland. Soon after, members of the public made contact with SEPA regarding water discolouration and large numbers of dead marine life washed ashore along the coast at a number of locations in the Firth of Clyde. Samples were sent for identification by SEPA and MSS analysts, who made contact with SAMS, confirming there was an ongoing bloom event covering the Firth of Clyde area (Fig. 2).

Combined SAMS and SEPA data illustrate the coverage and development of

this bloom through summer 2016 (Fig. 3). The bloom began in late July along the Ayrshire coast, and persisted at high abundance into September in Loch Ryan (Fig. 4). Cell density was sufficient to bring about hypoxic conditions three times [2, 3], and mass mortalities of a

variety of marine organisms were reported during these periods. One SEPA sample in Loch Ryan contained 3.5×10^7 cells per L^{-1} , which would have the potential to bring about total anoxia in the immediate vicinity upon termination of the bloom [2] (Fig. 5). This is reflected in the greater variety of organisms reported washed ashore dead in the Loch Ryan area.

Considerable effort has been made to describe and predict the conditions that initiate these blooms [4, 1], as the species has the potential to cause economic damage to the important finfish aquaculture sector on the west coast of Scotland. Blooms can occur as a result of advection from offshore [1, 5], or sparsely-distributed overwintering vegetative cells may act as a seed population when environmental conditions become favourable [5]. *Karenia mikimotoi* has also been observed to have a resting stage in the form of non-motile spherical cells [6] that could have the potential to initiate a bloom.

For part of the bloom period, the electronic bathing water advice signs administered by SEPA were automatically warning against swimming, due to heavy rainfall in the area which overloads wastewater treatment capac-

Fig. 2. The 2016 *K. mikimotoi* bloom. A: locations of reported mass mortalities; B: *K. mikimotoi* cells sampled at Ettrick Bay, Isle of Bute; C: dead lugworms washed up on the shoreline at Ettrick Bay; D: discoloured water in Loch Ryan.

Fig. 3. The progression of the bloom in the Firth of Clyde area. Letters indicate locations as described in Fig. 4.

ity resulting in discharge of untreated wastewater into the marine environment. This may contain additional nutrients of use to *K. mikimotoi* but these were not measured at the time of phytoplankton sampling. Rainfall is a factor in the initiation of *Karenia* blooms in the English Channel [7, 8] and more generally can establish conditions that lead to red tides set out by Smayda [9].

Acknowledgements

We thank Sheila Fraser at MSS for providing a second opinion on the identity of the cells. We also thank the phytoplankton monitoring team at SAMS and Lucy Kennedy, Lynne McDonald, and Michelle Tibbles at SEPA for assistance in sampling soon after reports of mass mortalities.

Fig. 4. The progression of the *K. mikimotoi* bloom by week in 2016, recorded at coastal monitoring sites around the Firth of Clyde.

Fig. 5. Theoretical effect of the *K. mikimotoi* bloom on background dissolved oxygen concentration (black horizontal dashed line: Firth of Clyde summer averaged SEPA data 2005-2015). Cell density was sufficient to cause hypoxia on 3 occasions at 4.59 mg L^{-1} [8] or once at 2 mg L^{-1} (grey dashed lines). An exceptionally dense bloom recorded by SEPA in Loch Ryan had potential to cause local anoxia (black vertical dotted line). Mass mortalities around the Firth of Clyde were reported on three dates (black asterisks).

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First evidence of high saxitoxin concentration in *Crassostrea iridiscens* associated with *Gymnodinium catenatum* blooms at Banderas Bay, Jalisco México

Fig. 1. Location of sampling stations in Banderas Bay Jalisco México during *Gymnodinium catenatum* bloom from March to June of 2017.

Banderas Bay has a long-standing history of toxic HABs. The presence of saxitoxins (STXs) had been associated with dinoflagellates belonging to the genus *Alexandrium* and with *Gymnodinium catenatum* [1, 2]. Blooms of both of these microalgae can pose a high risk for marine food resources to become contaminated with STXs, some of the most potent neurotoxins (PSP syndrome) which can prove fatally toxic to humans [3]. During 2017 the highest density of toxic *G. catenatum* and the first evidence of high STX concentrations in rock oysters (*Crassostrea iridiscens*), one of the most iconic species for the shellfish industry in the region, were recorded. A review of this event was carried out by the CIC-CUCOSTA-U de G in collaboration with the local health authorities of the Epidemiology Section (Department of Health Jalisco) for health protection and shellfish toxins regulatory purposes.

Banderas Bay is located on the western Mexican coast (20° 15' to 20° 47' N, 105° 15' to 105° 4' W) [4]. It has a total area of ~ 975 km², and is limited by Punta de Mita (north) and Cabo Corrientes (south), with a range of ~40 km between the two points (Fig. 1). The mean sea surface temperature is 26.4°C with a seasonal range from 23.3 °C dur-

ing winter-spring, to 30.0 °C during summer-autumn. The area has a complex hydrodynamic regime due to its location in a transitional area seasonally influenced by three important current systems: (1) the California Current that flows southward, bringing cold and low salinity water to the region, (2) the Costa Rican Coastal Current that flows northward, transporting warm waters of intermediate salinity, and (3) the warm and dense water of the Gulf of California, which is transported southward into the Banderas Bay region [4].

Samples of native *C. iridiscens* were obtained from three commercial oyster harvesting areas and the shellfish extracts prepared for toxin analysis at

the CCAYAC-COFEPRIS (Comisión del Control Analítico y Ampliación de Cobertura) laboratories, according to the Mexican Official NOM-242-SSA1-2009 standards and procedures [5]. Samples from *G. catenatum* bloom areas were collected from March to June at eight stations (E1-E8), stored in 500-ml plastic bottle and preserved with Lugol-acetate solution for identification and cell counts at a Leica® light microscope. Phytoplankton quantitative analyses were carried out with 20x and 40x magnification, using a 1 ml Sedgewick-Rafter settling chamber. Temperature and salinity were measured *in situ* using a YSI 85 multiparameter probe, and micrographs of *G. catenatum* obtained with a digital camera.

Based on mouse bioassay analysis (MBA), the maximum toxin concentration in *C. iridiscens* samples, 389.82 µg STX eq 100 g⁻¹ shellfish flesh, was observed at Station E-7 (Sheraton), the same location where the highest density of *G. catenatum* (2.42 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹) was found (Fig. 2). Regulations from the health authorities stipulate that bivalve molluscs for the market must not contain more than 80 µg STX eq 100 g⁻¹ tissue [5]. Given the magnitude of this PSP event, a temporary ban was immediately implemented by COFEPRIS authority, and a suspension of the extraction, commercialization and consumption of rock oysters was enforced through notification advice SST-CRS/599/2017, until STXs and *G. catenatum* densities in sea water dropped to safe levels. There were differences of three orders of magnitude (range, 3 x 10³ - 3 x 10⁶) in *G. catenatum* cell densities between the 8 sample sites (Fig. 3a). These densities were the the highest recorded since 2001 to date [1, 2]. During the toxic event, the mean surface temperature

Table 1. Toxin content (µg STX eq 100 g⁻¹) in soft tissue of *Crassostrea iridiscens* (rock oyster) from Banderas Bay, Jalisco, México at stations. E-8 (Velas), E-7 (Sheraton) and E-6 (Malecón).

Date	µg STX eq 100g ⁻¹	Station	Mean Temperature °C	Mean Salinity ups	Mean pH
March 14 th	32.52	E-8	22.85	33.48	8.28
March 24 th	389.82	E-7	24.52	33.43	8.34
April 6 th	48.86	E-7	22.5	33.26	8.18
April 7 th	not detected	E-7	22.5	33.26	8.18
May 8 th	38.61	E-7	-	-	-
June 6 th	not detected	E-7	25.1	33.16	8.14
June 23 th	59.52	E-6	23.12	33.25	16.23

Fig. 2. High saxitoxin concentration in *Crassostrea iridiscens* associated with *Gymnodinium catenatum* blooms in Banderas Bay, Jalisco México.

Fig. 3. Temporal (a) and spatial (b) variability of *G. catenatum* bloom in Banderas Bay, Jalisco México.

ranged from 22.19 to 25.26 °C, salinity remained almost constant (33.67-33.01) and pH values from 8.81 to 7.92. All these data coincide with “normal” seasonal patterns for this coastal area [4]. Previous data from the area have shown that increased in *G. catenatum* cell blooms exhibits a high spatial and temporal variability and are frequent in Banderas Bay (Fig. 3b). The highest densities are observed during winter-spring every year coinciding with the upwelling season.

Our findings during March and June 2017 suggest the accumulation of toxic cells of *G. catenatum* (Fig. 4) could explain the highest STX concentrations determined in shellfish from the Bay.

The standard mouse bioassay was used for regulatory purposes by the health authorities and there were no cases of public health illness during this

Fig. 4. Micrographs of live cells of *Gymnodinium catenatum* from Banderas Bay at 400x (a) and 200x (b); Seawater discoloration due to a *G. catenatum* patch during the bloom period in March-June 2017 (c) (Photos: M.C. Cortés-Lara)

event. This emphasizes the relevance of established monitoring programmes as an essential tool for timely detection and surveillance of the presence of HAB species and their toxins to protect public health in the coastal waters of Banderas Bay.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Ricardo Uribe Rodríguez from CCAYAC for his assistance with the toxin analyses and to Mercedes Azpeitia for her collaboration in this project.

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ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Blooms Dynamics

The report of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC) Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (ICES-IOC WGHABD) is now available on the ICES website (<http://www.ices.dk/community/groups/Pages/WGHABD.aspx>). ICES-IOC WGHABD met on three occasions to address 11 terms of reference (ToRs) during the three year reporting period; April 2015 (hosted by Teresa Moita and Alexandra Silva, IPMA, Lisbon, Portugal), April 2016 (hosted by Raffaele Siano, IFREMER, Brest, France), and April 2017 (hosted by Anke Kremp, SYKE, Helsinki, Finland (Fig. 1)).

Three terms of reference contributed to the work of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IOC IPHAB). A manuscript on fish killing algae produced by ICES-IOC WGHABD will feed into the IPHAB task team on fish killing algae. ICES-IOC WGHABD have updated and quality controlled data in the IOC-ICES-PICES Harmful Algal Event Database (HAEDAT). Maps showing the regional distribution of harmful algal events presented at ICES-IOC WGHABD using data from HAEDAT from 2014 – 2016 are included in the report. ICES-IOC WGHABD is producing

a Harmful Algal Event status report for the ICES area during 2018. This status report will be the ICES contribution to the Global HAB Status Report currently in production (see article by Hallegraeff et al. in this issue).

A dynamic range of new findings were presented each year with summaries included in ICES-IOC WGHABD annual reports from 2015 - 2017. These presentations encompassed studies performed with the latest technologies or approaches and include the use of technologies such as the Imaging Flow Cytobot to examine HABs in the USA and Sweden, citizen science in France, the use of sediment cores to reconstruct the history of toxic *Nodularia spumigena* blooms in the Baltic Sea and Oslofjorden, development of early warning systems in the UK and social unrest in Chile as a result of HABs.

ICES-IOC WGHABD also reviewed the OSPAR JAMP Eutrophication Guidelines on phytoplankton species composition and participated in the subsequent advisory drafting group ADGJAMP during 2015. The WG also contributed to the organization of the ICES-PICES-IOC scientific symposium on climate change and harmful algal blooms held 19 – 22nd May 2015, Gothenburg, Sweden. More than 60 scien-

tists from across the globe participated. A major output of this symposium is the peer reviewed publication, Wells, M.L. et al., (2015). Harmful algal blooms and climate change: Learning from the past and present to forecast the future. *Harmful Algae*, 49:68–93.

The WG also reviewed the use of molecular probes, qPCR methods targeting toxin producing genes and metabarcoding of HABs, as well as the state of knowledge of BMAA, the amino compound β -methylamino alanine. The dynamics of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in the Iberian Peninsula, *Alexandrium minutum* in the Bay of Brest and *A. ostentifidii* and cyanobacteria in the Baltic were also reviewed with summaries of presentations included in ICES-IOC WGHABD annual reports.

The next meeting of ICES-IOC WGHABD will take place from 23rd – 26th April 2018, hosted by Dr Margarita Fernandez Tejedor from IRTA, Sant Carles de la Ràpita, Tarragona, Spain.

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Fig. 1. Participants at the ICES-IOC WGHABD hosted by Dr. Anke Kremp at SYKE, Helsinki, Finland, April 2017.

SEAFDEC-MFRD Regional Training Course in Malaysia

Harmful algal blooms (HAB) and their socio-economic impacts are recognized internationally due to the negative impacts from HABs on the coastal ecosystem, safety and security of food and drinking water, and human health hazards. Some incidents and occurrences are cross national borders and cover wide sea areas.

HAB events especially affect the rapidly growing aquaculture industries in Southeast Asian countries, HAB monitoring programmes have been established and implemented. These programmes have been hampered by the lack of trained manpower in HAB monitoring. The Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center (SEAFDEC) through the Marine Fisheries Research Development (MFRD) program has implemented a series of training workshops to enhance the expertise of personnel from its member countries. A regional training course with the theme "Specimen Preservation and its Application in HAB Monitoring and Studies" was successfully conducted at Bachok Marine Research Station, Institute of Ocean and Earth Science, University of Malaya.

The 4-day training course, hosted by Dr. Po Teen Lim, was attended by 21 participants from nine Southeast Asian countries (Brunei, Cambodia, Indone-

sia, Laos, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Singapore, and Vietnam) (Fig. 1). The Chief of MFRD, Mr. Soon Eong Yeap in his official remarks, stressed the continuous commitment to support HABs and biotoxin programmes initiated through the Japanese Trust Fund on HABs and biotoxins. In the welcoming remarks, Dr. Lim highlighted the need for capacity building and strengthening of HAB research collaboration in the region (Fig. 2).

The project leader of the UNESCO IOC WESTPAC HAB program, Dr. Mitsunori Iwataki, provided support by contributing reference and teaching materials. All lectures were followed by practical sessions on HAB monitoring and studies. An introductory lecture given by Dr. Lim highlighted HAB occurrences, types, causative species and impacts. Dr. Chui Pin Leaw provided lectures on the current detection technologies applied in HAB research and monitoring. The practical sessions included sampling devices and sampling processing, type of preservatives and stains, single-cell polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and real-time quantitative PCR for species detection and enumeration (Fig. 3). During the practical session, a contest on the best sketch of a HAB species was held and three par-

ticipants from Thailand, Cambodia, and Philippines were awarded prizes. During the discussion session, participants expressed their interest on certain topics for the future training course. The 4-day training course ended with a certificate presentation ceremony.

Authors

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Fig. 2. Observing phytoplankton specimens by microscopes.

Fig. 3. Demonstrating qPCR assay for species detection.

Fig. 1. Participants of the SEAFDEC Regional Training Course at Bachok Marine Research Station, University of Malaya.

Forthcoming events

Workshop on morpho-molecular methods for the study of dino-flagellate cysts

Monday 12th and Tuesday 13th February 2018

Location: Cawthron Institute, 98 Halifax Street East, Nelson 7010, New Zealand

Organisers: Kirsty Smith, Lesley Rhodes (Cawthron Institute), Kenneth Neil Mertens (Ifremer, France)

We invite you to participate in this workshop which will discuss traditional morphological methods and novel molecular methods (e.g. qPCR, metabarcoding) and how to combine these techniques to achieve the best results when identifying dinoflagellates and their cysts. Other protists can also be included if there is interest from participants. During the workshop the pros and cons of traditional microscopic techniques versus novel molecular techniques will be discussed and demonstrated; incubation techniques will also be demonstrated.

Participants are invited to present their research during the workshop, and bring samples/slides to study. If coming from overseas, please check with Kirsty Smith for quarantine requirements.

The workshop, which includes complimentary lunches on Monday and Tuesday, is free and will require registration only (no charge). Participants have to pay their trip and accommodation. Please contact the organisers for suggestions on travel to Nelson and accommodation.

Please let us know as soon as possible if you wish to attend as the number of participants is limited to 20.

Hope to see you there!

Kenneth Mertens, Kirsty Smith & Lesley Rhodes, Cawthron Institute, New Zealand

Email: kirsty.smith@cawthron.org.nz

ICES-IOC-IMO Working Group on Ballast and Other Ship Vectors

5-7 March 2018

The next meeting of the Working Group on Ballast and Other Ship Vectors (WGBOSV) will be held in Caniçal, Madeira, Portugal from 5 to 7 March 2017.

If you, or any expert from your country, wish to attend, please contact the chair of the WGBOSV, Dr. Baily: Sarah.Bailey@dfo-mpo.gc.ca

SETAC Europe Conference, Rome

13-17 May 2017

In the framework of the next SETAC Europe conference (Rome, 13-17 May 2017), within Track 4 "Ecological risk assessment and human health risk assessment of chemicals mixtures and stressors and risk mitigation strategies", the following session has been proposed.

4.6 Do human activities and global change influence the occurrence, toxicity and pathogenicity of marine harmful microorganisms affecting seafood safety?

Co-chairs: Jorge Diogène, Angelo Maggione

Variations of environmental factors associated with human activities and global change may have direct and indirect impacts on the occurrence, dominance, persistence, adaptation, toxicity and pathogenicity of marine microorganisms. For example, changes in climate may allow originally tropical phytoplankton species to expand their spatial and temporal distribution to previously temperate waters. Shellfish, finfish and other marine organisms can accumulate in their organs pathogenic microorganisms or the toxins they can produce, which are transferred within food webs reaching humans through consumption of seafood. Changes in the biology and ecology of pathogenic and toxin-producing microorganisms could therefore determine an increase in the

number and intensity of seafood-related diseases. Microorganisms and toxins not previously reported in European seas are now appearing, including areas that are intensive producers of seafood. This is a cause of concern as some of these emerging hazards are not included in current legislation and monitoring programs.

This session has different objectives. A major objective will be to gather information and data on variations in the occurrence, intensity, species composition, toxicity and pathogenicity of harmful marine microorganisms. Particular attention will be focused on biologically relevant areas (hatching, nourishing areas), sensitive areas (estuaries and coastal zones), harvesting, fishing areas or areas occupied by aquaculture facilities. These data should include information on environmental variables linked to climate change (pH, temperature, salinity, oxygen, nutrients etc).

This information is crucial for the development of models that may be able to predict the spatio-temporal distribution of harmful microorganisms, their toxicity/pathogenicity and the bioaccumulation of marine toxins in marine organisms. These models may provide management tools for the design of sampling programs and the implementation of mitigation strategies, taking into consideration the possible co-occurrence of different harmful organisms. This session will also identify research needs and knowledge gaps in understanding how environmental changes will affect the microbial community, in particular the mechanisms underlying their sensitivity to changes (acclimation, physiological plasticity, strain diversity etc). It will also intend to favour a critical analysis of how human activities and global change are impacting the ocean microbial community and discuss future trends in research to better assess this issue, with particular focus on the impact on seafood safety and public health.

The deadline for abstracts submission is November 29th, 2017.

More info at: <http://bit.ly/2yj10gv>

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Rex Munday in Memoriam

Dr Rex Munday, an internationally renowned toxicologist, sadly passed away on the 20th July this year. His wife Christine, daughter Sarah (Finch) and son John were with him. Rex published with all his family at different times, an example being the paper Munday, Munday and Munday, 2005, J. Agric. Food Chem. 53, pp 9695–9700!

Rex, an organic chemist (graduated Sheffield University, UK), arrived in 1979 for a two year stint at AgResearch, Hamilton, New Zealand, as a facial eczema research fellow and ended up staying for nearly four decades. He was instrumental in developing the zinc bolus technology which provides a practical solution to protect animals from facial eczema. In 2009 his research was recognised with a Kudos Lifetime Achievement Award (Kudos Science Trust, Waikato, New Zealand). It is worth checking out his own explanation of his research at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bimDOJPbi_o.

Rex also researched isothiocyanates, which are present in Brassica vegetables, and demonstrated that they afford protection against bladder cancer in experimental animals, raising the possibility that these natural, non-toxic substances could be valuable for cancer prevention in humans.

As “Principal scientist, toxicology” at AgResearch, he rapidly became internationally recognised for his work for the government funded Safe New Zealand Seafood programme, collaborating with the Cawthron Institute to determine the implications of micro-algal biotoxins for human safety. The work saw him involved with the FAO/WHO/IOC expert panel on shellfish toxins and expert panels of EFSA on setting regulatory limits for biotoxins.

He was on the organising committee for the 16th International conference on Harmful Algae, Wellington, New Zealand, 2014, and presented a plenary lecture on “Risk assessment of seafood toxins”. Many readers of HANews will remember him for his succinct, informative and often entertaining presentations over many years. He has chapters on biotoxin toxicity in many books, for example:

- Munday R 2013. Toxicity of Cyclic Imines. In ‘Toxins and Biologically Active Compounds from Marine Microalgae’, G.-P. Rossini (ed.),

- Munday R 2013. Toxicology of Seafood Toxins: A Critical Review. In ‘Seafood and Freshwater Toxins: Pharmacology, Physiology and Detection’, Third Edition. L. M. Botana (ed.) and, about to be published,

- Munday R 2017 Toxicology of Seafood Toxins: Animal Studies and Mechanisms of Action. In Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry: Recent Advances on the Analysis of Marine Toxins. J Diogene and M Campas (eds.).

Rex was very sure that oral toxicity was the way to go for the setting of biotoxin regulations. He wrote a comment about Paralytic shellfish toxins (PSTs), which was to be submitted to HANews, and which stated with his usual clarity that: *“New analytical techniques allow the concentration of the various PSTs in a seafood sample to be determined with accuracy and precision. But the toxicity of the different compounds in the mixture of toxins varies, so in order to determine the risk of the sample to human health, we need to know the relative toxicities of the different compounds in the mixture. This permits the calculation of ‘Toxicity Equivalence Factors (TEFs)’.* A major compound in the mixture (in the case of the PSTs this is saxitoxin) is given a TEF of 1.0. If the toxicity of a compound (Compound X) in the mixture is half that of saxitoxin, its TEF is 0.5. If the toxicity of another compound (Compound Y) is twice as toxic as saxitoxin, its TEF is 2.0. So, if the analytical data shows concentrations of saxitoxin, Compound X and

Compound Y in the sample of 0.5 µg/g, 0.2 µg/g and 1 µg/g respectively, the overall toxicity can be calculated as $1 \times 0.5 + 0.5 \times 0.2 + 1 \times 2 = 2.6 \mu\text{g/g}$.

In the past, TEFs for PSTs have been based on toxicity by intraperitoneal injection in mice. This is inappropriate, since human exposure to such toxins is via the oral route, and there is no correlation between toxicity by intraperitoneal injection and that by oral administration. The acute oral toxicity of a number of PSTs has now been determined in mice, and these data have been used to calculate TEFs that are relevant to the human situation. The new data on oral toxicity will lead to a more precise evaluation of the levels of PSTs in seafood that are safe for human consumption.”

Rex was highly regarded by his colleagues and was a mentor to many younger scientists. We will all miss his sage advice and his delightfully dry sense of humour. His contribution to HAB science has been immense.

A small sample of Rex’s >150 key HAB related publications

Munday R, Briggs L, Truman P, Gooneratne R, Edwards P, Pascal S M 2012. Novel toxins produced by the dinoflagellate *Karenia brevisulcata*. Harmful Algae, 13, 47-57.

Munday R, Quilliam M A, LeBlanc P, Lewis N, Gallant P, Sperker S A, Ewart H S, MacKinnon S L 2012. Investigations into the toxicology of spirulides, a group of marine phycotoxins. Toxins 4, 1-14.

Munday R., Selwood A I, Rhodes L 2012. Acute toxicity of pinnatoxins E, F and G to mice. Toxicon, 60, 995-999.

Munday R. 2011. Palytoxin toxicology: Animal studies. Toxicon, 57, 470-477.

Lesley L. Rhodes, Tim Harwood, Andy Selwood, Kirsty Smith, Lincoln Mackenzie Cawthron Institute, Nelson, New Zealand

Paul McNabb
IECU Manager, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Nelson, New Zealand

Rex Munday's HAB research highlights

Discovery of Tetrodotoxin in grey side-gilled sea slugs: "Rex had a sharp wit, best illustrated with an anecdote from 2013. We had collected hundreds of samples to explain why dogs were dying on Auckland beaches and sent twelve to Rex for toxicity screening using live mice. The next day we didn't dare phone to ask for an update but waited for an email, knowing Rex would be hard at work. Soon that email arrived and briefly, but accurately, described the materials and method used. This was followed by a list of each sample in numerical order with a short description of symptoms observed, most being 'no symptoms'. But next to one sample were the words 'death in seconds'. We immediately phoned Rex and asked what he thought of this result. His reply was 'Well, yes, that is an interesting sample. I have diluted it 10,000 fold and it's still killing a mouse in under one minute'. I'll never know if he was having us on or if he was just that truly objective and professional, he was often both."

Paul McNabb

The toxicity of anatoxin congeners from cyanobacteria: "Working in Hamilton on toxins from cyanobacteria I had heard the tales of the legendary Rex Munday and had always longed for the chance to work with him. A year ago, the opportunity was realised as we set out to investigate the acute toxicity of the anatoxin congeners, which are produced by the *Phormidium* which plagues many rivers around New Zealand. For a young scientist Rex's level-headed guidance was a god-send and allowed us to navigate a safe course through the minefield which research can be. Anyone who has worked near me whilst I'm extracting *Phormidium* samples knows that the aroma is slightly off-putting. Rex had the following succinctly simple statement on the difficulties of trying to feed these musty extracts to mice; 'For experiments on

toxicity by feeding, mice are trained to eat small quantities of cream cheese. When they eat the offered cream cheese within a matter of seconds, the appropriate weight of freeze dried test material is mixed with the cheese and given to the mice. However, mice trained to eat cream cheese refused to eat the mixture with *Phormidium* extract and a different approach was required.' Rex's solution ended up being quite simple and effective; a positive displacement pipette was used to place the food on to the mouse's tongue and the food was instantly/instinctively gobbled it up. Rex's innovation and experience will be sorely missed by the toxic cyanobacteria research community of New Zealand."

Jonathan Puddick

Oral toxicity of paralytic shellfish toxins: "Rex was a key cog in the Safe NZ Seafood research programme, well-liked and respected by his colleagues both in NZ and abroad. He had an easy-going nature and great sense of humour. His work on the toxicity of various marine toxins over a long period of time made him an expert in this field. Rex published his findings in numerous journal articles, book chapters and featured on a number of expert working groups. He was firm in his belief that the toxicity assessment of marine toxins should be based on oral exposure rather than intraperitoneal administration, as this more accurately represents their route of exposure in humans. In recent years, Rex undertook a large piece of work on the acute toxicity of paralytic shellfish toxins, which represent a class of structurally related marine toxins that are problematic in NZ and other parts of the world. His findings are internationally important and will result in changes to the way this toxin class is regulated and will undoubtedly improve human health protection from exposure to these potent marine toxins.

On a personal level Rex was both a mentor and a friend. He always took the time to ask how I was going and how my family was tracking. He was terrific to bounce ideas off and was able to provide guidance on how to deal with work matters that were not going so well. I really appreciated this gesture. Thanks Rex, you will be missed."

Tim Harwood

The identification of pinnatoxins in pacific oysters: "I worked with Rex on some very interesting projects over the past 15 years. He was a fantastic person to collaborate with as he was an extremely good scientist, an inspirational mentor and had a great sense of humour to boot. My job as a natural products chemist was to provide Rex with compounds for toxicological evaluation. Rex always enjoyed giving us chemists a hard time, and because of his background in chemistry he knew how to do this really well. He would take great joy in seeing the reaction on our faces when he explained how much toxin would be required for a toxicological study, knowing that this would be a painstaking and near impossible task.

One of the highlights of my early career was working with Rex on a research project to identify unknown toxins in shellfish from South Australia. Several oyster growing areas in South Australia had been closed down due to the presence of an unidentified fast acting toxin. The project was extremely successful; we discovered three novel toxins, pinnatoxins E, F and G and determined their acute toxicity. This resulted in the re-opening of oyster growing areas in South Australia and in New Zealand. To be honest, I was nervous about taking on such a complex project due to my lack of experience. Rex's support and mentorship gave me the confidence to be able to complete that challenging task."

Andy Selwood

Oostende OBIS/HAEDAT training workshop participants.

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Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 59:
10 December 2017

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Lay-out

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The publication of Harmful Algae News is sponsored
by the Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen